

trial and error method⁴⁻⁶. The observed values fit well in cubic system to give a unit cell with lattice constants $a=b=c=6.7011 \text{ \AA}$ and cell volume $=300.91 \text{ \AA}^3$ for the first complex and in tetragonal system to give a unit cell with lattice constant $a=8.017 \text{ \AA}$, $c=8.117 \text{ \AA}$ and cell volume $=521.70 \text{ \AA}^3$ for the second complex. Substitution of this cell volume primitive lattice ($n=1$) for the first complex gives the theoretical value of density equal to 4.3258 g cm^{-3} and substitution of cell volume primitive lattice ($n=1$) for the second complex gives the theoretical value of density equal to 2.3003 g cm^{-3} . The experimental values of densities of the two complexes have been found to be 4.3479 and 2.3275 g cm^{-3} which are fairly in good agreement within the limits of experimental errors.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Chairman, S.S.C.U., Indian Institute of Science, for X-ray diffraction data.

References

1. T. R. GOUDAR, S. M. SHINDAGI and G. S. NADAGOUDA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 632.
2. B. D. CULLITY, "Elements of X-Ray Diffraction", Wesley, London, 1959.
3. B. F. LEVINE, *Phy. Rev. (B)*, 1975, **87**, 2591.
4. N. F. M. HENRY, H. LIPSON and W. A. WOOSTER, "Interpretation of X-Ray Diffraction Photographs", McMillan, London, p. 123.
5. M. J. BURGER, "X-Ray Crystallography", Wiley, New York, 1953, p. 100.
6. H. S. PRISHR, H. P. BOKSEY and A. J. C. WILSON, "X-Ray Diffraction by Polycrystalline Materials", Institute of Physics, London, 1956, p. 344.

Synthesis and Characterisation of $(OCN)_2$ - $Co(NCSHgR)_2$ ($R=CH_3, C_2H_5, n-C_4H_9$ or C_6H_5) and $L_2(OCN)_2Co(NCSHgR)_2$ (L =methanol, pyridine or nicotinamide)

S. B. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, M. L. K. College, Balrampur-271 201

Manuscript received 8 October 1987, revised 17 May 1988,
accepted 11 June 1988

WITH a view to study bonding mode of cyanate and thiocyanate, $(OCN)_2Co(NCSHgR)_2$ where $R=CH_3, C_2H_5, n-C_4H_9$ or C_6H_5 and their adducts with methanol(MeOH), pyridine(py) and nicotinamide(nia) were prepared. The effect of steric hindrance, caused by organic groups attached to Hg^{II} , has been studied on the bonding mode of cyanate and thiocyanate groups.

Experimental

All materials and manipulations were done as reported earlier¹.

Preparation of complexes: $Co(NCO)_2L_4$ ($L=py, nia$) and $RHgCl$ ($R=CH_3, C_2H_5, n-C_4H_9$ or C_6H_5) were prepared according to literature methods²⁻⁶. Methylmercury thiocyanate was prepared by the metathesis of mercury thiocyanate and dimethylmercury as described earlier⁶. Ethylmercury thiocyanate was prepared by the reaction of ethylmercury chloride and potassium thiocyanate in acetone in 1 : 1 molar ratio, on stirring for 1 h. The filtrate after removal of precipitated potassium chloride was concentrated by evaporation under reduced pressure. C_2H_5HgSCN was precipitated by water from the concentrate, which was filtered, washed with water and dried over P_2O_5 under reduced pressure. It was recrystallised from ethanol and dried in vacuum oven at 50° .

Butylmercury thiocyanate was prepared similarly. Phenylmercury thiocyanate was prepared by the method reported earlier⁷. $(OCN)_2Co(NCSHgCH_3)_2$ was prepared by stirring ethanolic solution of $Co(NCO)_2$ (1 mmol) and CH_3HgSCN (2 mmol), for ~ 36 h. The precipitated blue compound was filtered, washed with ethyl acetate and dried under reduced pressure. Ethyl, n-butyl and phenylmercury thiocyanate derivatives were similarly prepared.

$(Py)_2(OCN)_2Co(NCSHgR)_2$ were similarly prepared by stirring acetone solution of $Co(NCO)_2 \cdot 4py$ (1 mmol) in different flasks for ~ 36 h. The resulting pink complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallised from acetone and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 . Nicotinamide complexes were prepared similarly. Methanol complexes were prepared by stirring acetone solutions of $RHgSCN$ (2 mmol) with methanol solutions of $Co(NCO)_2$ in different flasks for ~ 48 h. The resulting pink complexes were filtered, washed with methanol and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 .

Alternatively, all complexes could also be prepared by stirring suspensions of Lewis acids, $(OCN)_2Co(NCSHgR)_2$, and ligands in separate flasks in ethanol in 1 : 2 molar ratio for ~ 36 h.

Cobalt was estimated as cobalt anthranilate, sulphur as barium sulphate and mercury as mercury sulphide, gravimetrically. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. Analytical results are presented in Table 1.

Molar conductance values of $0.001 M$ solutions in DMF, and molecular weights in DMSO (freezing point depression method) and room temperature magnetic moment values are presented in Table 1. Ir ($4000-200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), far-ir ($500-50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and uv-visible ($2500-200 \text{ nm}$) spectra were recorded as described earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

Lewis acids: $(OCN)_2Co(NCSHgR)_2$ ($R=CH_3, C_2H_5, n-C_4H_9$ or C_6H_5): The positions of ν_{CN} , ν_{CS} , ν_{HgC} , δ_{SCN} and ν_{HgS} observed at about 2180,

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff}	Δ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
				S	N	Co	Hg		
A	Blue	640 (689)	210	9.04 (9.27)	7.86 (8.11)	8.68 (8.55)	28.91 (29.05)	4.54	36.94
A.2py	Pink	812 (847)	215	7.39 (7.54)	9.70 (9.90)	6.42 (6.95)	22.88 (22.64)	5.15	41.50
A.2nia	Pink	890 (933)	218	6.72 (6.85)	11.48 (12.00)	5.93 (6.31)	20.98 (21.46)	5.12	42.10
A.2MeOH	Pink	720 (753)	227	8.03 (8.48)	6.84 (7.42)	7.24 (7.82)	25.96 (26.59)	4.97	50.70
B	Blue	689 (717)	220	8.56 (8.91)	7.34 (7.79)	7.86 (8.20)	27.28 (27.90)	4.44	40.14
B.2py	Pink	823 (875)	212	7.01 (7.30)	9.10 (9.55)	6.40 (6.73)	22.62 (22.88)	5.08	43.40
B.2nia	Pink	911 (961)	220	6.31 (6.65)	10.42 (11.65)	5.91 (6.13)	20.52 (20.84)	5.10	47.50
B.2MeOH	Pink	721 (781)	217	7.90 (8.18)	6.94 (7.16)	7.28 (7.54)	25.48 (26.63)	5.01	43.70
C	Blue	694 (773)	230	8.16 (8.26)	7.07 (7.23)	7.18 (7.62)	25.72 (26.90)	4.50	38.21
C.2py	Pink	920 (931)	217	6.42 (6.86)	8.90 (9.00)	6.18 (6.33)	21.32 (21.51)	5.20	40.90
C.2nia	Pink	945 (1017)	222	6.01 (6.28)	10.65 (11.01)	5.42 (5.79)	19.44 (19.69)	5.19	45.10
C.2MeOH	Pink	798 (837)	234	7.48 (7.65)	6.20 (6.68)	6.78 (7.04)	22.86 (23.92)	5.04	48.80
D	Blue	754 (813)	225	7.52 (7.86)	6.80 (6.87)	7.14 (7.24)	23.53 (24.63)	4.52	42.70
D.2py	Pink	863 (971)	218	6.36 (6.58)	8.28 (8.64)	5.92 (6.06)	19.46 (20.62)	5.18	43.18
D.2nia	Pink	977 (1057)	225	5.89 (6.04)	9.83 (10.60)	5.41 (5.57)	17.85 (18.95)	5.09	48.80
D.2MeOH	Pink	786 (877)	238	7.10 (7.28)	6.12 (6.37)	6.80 (6.71)	21.94 (22.83)	4.98	44.50

*A = $(\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgCH}_3)_2$, B = $(\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgC}_2\text{H}_5)_2$, C = $(\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHg } n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2$, D = $(\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$.

738, 543, 440 and 238 cm^{-1} , respectively, in the solid phase spectra of RHgSCN , shifted to 2 165, 765, 570, 450 and 240 cm^{-1} , respectively, on formation of the complex, $(\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgR})_2$. These changes indicate that the thiocyanate of RHgSCN becomes bridged by coordination with Co^{II} through its nitrogen end⁹. The presence of two bands for ν_{CN} , ν_{CO} and δ_{NCO} each in the ranges 2 190–2 210, 1 320–1 380 and 650–680 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicate N-bonded terminal cyanates^{2,8,9}. In thiocyanate region also two bands are observed for ν_{CN} , ν_{CS} and δ_{NCS} each, in the range 2 140–2 165, 710–740 and 450–480 cm^{-1} , respectively, showing the presence of bridged thiocyanates⁹. Hence thiocyanate and cyanate are linked at *cis*-positions to Co^{II} as only one band could be observed in each region if these were at *trans*-positions. In far-ir region, two bands in each of the range 270–285 and 245–265 cm^{-1} , are observed due to $\nu_{\text{Co-NCO}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Co-NCS}}$, respectively. Bands due to $\delta_{\text{NCO-N}}$ of cyanate and thiocyanate are observed at 150–170 cm^{-1} and due to LML at 180–200 cm^{-1} . A band observed at 75–85 cm^{-1} is assigned to δ_{SHgC} mode.

The electronic spectra of these complexes show the presence of two bands at 16 100–16 980 and 7 620–7 910 cm^{-1} , due to the transitions, ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$ (ν_3), respectively. These

together with μ_{eff} value of 4.44–4.54 B.M. and spectral parameters, Dq (442–467 cm^{-1}), B' (720–751 cm^{-1}) and β (0.71–0.77), indicate tetrahedral geometry (I) around Co^{II} in these complexes.

Total softness difference values, $\Delta TE_n^{\ddagger}(\text{Co-Hg})$ (matching constant)⁹, suggests the following sequence for the stability of thiocyanate bridge in these complexes: $(\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgCH}_3)_2 > (\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgC}_2\text{H}_5)_2 > (\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHg } n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)_2 > (\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$. The Dq values of the complexes suggest following decreasing order for RHgSCN in the spectrochemical series: $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{HgSCN} < \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgSCN} < \text{CH}_3\text{HgSCN} < \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{HgSCN}$, and the nephelauxetic parameter (β) are in the order: $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgSCN} > \text{CH}_3\text{HgSCN} > \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{HgSCN} > n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{HgSCN}$. The lowest value of β for $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{HgSCN}$ suggests that it has highest

covalency among these ligands towards coordination to Co^{II} .

Adducts: $L_2(\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgR})_2$ ($R = \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $L = \text{py}, \text{nia}, \text{MeOH}$): The ir spectral bands due to $\nu_{\text{CN}}, \nu_{\text{CS}}$ and δ_{NCS} of thiocyanate and $\nu_{\text{CN}}, \nu_{\text{CO}}$ and δ_{NCO} of cyanate appear in the ranges corresponding to bridged thiocyanate and nitrogen bonded terminal cyanate groups. These positions are comparable with those of Lewis acids with slight changes due to the change in stereochemistry around Co^{II} . It is also indicated by a negative shift of $10\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the position of $\nu_{\text{Co-NCS}}$ bands on complex formation. Pyridine and nicotinamide show features of coordination through ring nitrogen and methanol through oxygen of alcoholic group. The presence of $\nu_{\text{Co-L}}$ band in the range $290\text{--}310\text{ cm}^{-1}$ consistent with previous ranges for this mode, supports the coordination of the ligands to Co^{II} . The presence of only one band for $\nu_{\text{Co-L}}$ also suggests the addition of ligands at *trans*-positions of the octahedra¹⁰.

Molar conductance values (Table 1) of these adducts in DMF indicate their non-electrolytic nature. The pink pyridine complex is converted to blue parent Lewis acid on heating at 80° in vacuum indicating coordination of pyridine to Co^{II} . Electronic spectra of all these adducts show the presence of three absorption bands in the ranges $20\,200\text{--}21\,980, 17\,094\text{--}19\,047$ and $9\,025\text{--}10\,152\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are assigned to the transitions, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), respectively. These positions, values of spectral parameters, Dq ($911\text{--}1\,410\text{ cm}^{-1}$), B' ($753\text{--}953\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and β ($0.78\text{--}0.98$), magnetic moment ($4.97\text{--}5.18\text{ B.M.}$) and pink colour indicate octahedral geometry (II) around Co^{II} in these complexes.

$R = \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5, n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $L = \text{py}, \text{nia}$ or MeOH

II

Higher values of $\Delta E_{\text{nm}}^\ddagger(\text{Co-L})$ (11.08 for $L = \text{py}$, 13.23 for $L = \text{nia}$) compared to those for $\Delta E_{\text{nm}}^\ddagger(\text{Hg-L})$ (5.23 for $L = \text{py}$, 7.38 for $L = \text{nia}$), again favour coordination of ligands to Co^{II} . This is also true due to the higher values ($37.52\text{--}42.75$) of $\Delta TE_n^\ddagger(\text{Co-Hg})$ obtained on considering ligands attached to Co^{II} compared to ($0.83\text{--}3.12$) for ligands attached to Hg^{II} . Total softness difference values, $\Delta TE_n^\ddagger(\text{Co-Hg})$, suggest the following sequence for the stability of thiocyanate bridge, for Lewis acids: $(\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgCH}_3)_2 < (\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgC}_2\text{H}_5)_2 < (\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgC}_4\text{H}_9)_2 < (\text{OCN})_2\text{Co}(\text{NCSHgC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$. This sequence is also in accordance with the steric effect caused by alkyl

or aryl groups. Stability of nicotinamide adduct is found higher than pyridine adduct due to higher value of $\Delta E_{\text{nm}}^\ddagger(\text{Co-L})$ for the former.

References

1. S. B. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 309.
2. A. H. NORBURY and A. I. P. SINHA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 1598.
3. J. NELSON and S. M. NELSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 1597.
4. H. GILMAN and R. H. BROWN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 3314.
5. C. S. MARWEL and V. L. GOULD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 820.
6. E. E. AVNSLEY, N. N. GREENWOOD and M. J. SPRAGUE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 2395.
7. K. DEHNICK, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1967, **9**, 1117.
8. R. A. BAILEY, S. L. KOZAK, T. W. MICHELSEN and W. N. MILLS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **6**, 407.
9. P. P. SINGH and D. D. S. YADAV, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, **41**, 1105.
10. P. P. SINGH and A. K. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 928.

Formation Constants of Bivalent Transition Metal Complexes with some 1-(3-Phenyl-5-hydroxy-4-isoxazolylazo)-4-sulphonic Acids

CH. NAGARJUN RAO, K. C. RAJANNA, Y. UMA DEVI
and

P. K. SAIPRAKASH*

Department of Chemistry, Nizam College, Osmania University,
Hyderabad-500 001

Manuscript received 23 October 1987, revised 7 June 1988,
accepted 15 June 1988

THE azo-dye compounds of sulphonic acid comprising pyridine moiety have gained much prominence as analytical reagents in complexometric titrations^{1,2}. Isoxazoles having arylazo group at position-4 have been reported to possess antidiabetic and agricultural fungicidal activities^{3,4}. Though the formation of a variety of transition metal complexes are well-documented in literature, such studies are lacking with 1-(3-phenyl-5-hydroxy-4-isoxazolylazo)-4-sulphonic acid (PHI-4S) compounds (1). In this paper, we report the formation constants of some bivalent transition metal complexes with PHI-4S.

$R = \text{H}, \text{CH}_3, \text{OCH}_3, \text{Br}$.

1

Experimental

The reagents used are of AnalaR or G.R. (E. Merck) grade. Aqueous solutions of metal nitrates